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SYNTHESIS OF STATE OBSERVERS AND CONSTRUCTION OF A CLOSED-LOOP CONTROL SYSTEM BASED ON THEM

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Abstract. This article elucidates the principles of synthesizing state observers used for controlled objects with limited direct state measurement capabilities. The observer calculates the internal states of the object based on its mathematical model and adapts to the real object by reducing the error through comparison with the measured output. The paper presents the complete structure of the observer, methods for determining the L-matrix that defines its dynamics, the separability of control and observation processes, and the principle of duality between them, supported by theoretical foundations. The synthesis of a practical observer for an electric drive, a model of an astatic observer, and criteria for selecting the L-matrix to meet speed and stability requirements are provided. Additionally, discrete observer equations, real-time algorithms for microcontroller implementation, their flowcharts, and the possibilities of detecting and compensating for external influences are discussed.

Keywords: state observer, observer synthesis, regulator state, duality principle, L-matrix, electric drive control, astatic observer, dynamic system model, discrete observer, microcontroller control algorithm.

Introduction

The effectiveness of modern control systems largely depends on the accurate assessment and real-time monitoring of the internal state of the object. However, in many technical systems, especially mechatronics, electric drives, chemical processes or complex mechanical objects, the possibility of direct measurement of internal states is limited. Sometimes this is practically expensive, physically impossible or can negatively affect the reliability of the system. Therefore, the theory of state observers has emerged as one of the most important areas of automatic control, which makes it possible to determine internal coordinates without direct measurement. The state observer calculates the state of the object based on a mathematical model and reduces the observation error by comparing it with the measured output signal. This mechanism significantly simplifies the control system, since it makes it possible to reduce the number of additional sensors, complex measuring devices or sensors requiring high accuracy. The main goal of synthesizing observers in control theory is to create a mathematical model that can accurately reproduce the state of an object in real time. This not only optimizes control functions, but also increases stability, reduces

sensitivity to external and internal influences, and expands the adaptive capabilities of the system.[1,3]

Another important aspect of state observers is that, when working together with regulators, they are able to radically improve the dynamic characteristics of the entire system. In particular, when the internal coordinates determined using the observer are transmitted to the input of the regulator, a significant increase in control quality is observed. The system's response to disruptive influences is accelerated, excessive fluctuations are reduced, and the stability of the process is ensured at a high level. The concept of separability of observer and regulator processes also plays an important role in the theory. According to this principle, the dynamics of the regulator and the dynamics of the observer can be designed independently, as a result of which the engineering process is simplified and full control over the overall system parameters is created. State observers are especially widely used in electric drives, since in this area it is not always possible to fully measure state variables such as current, speed, and torque. Accordingly, with the help of the observer, the internal dynamics of the system are restored, the effect of external loads is determined and their compensation

becomes possible. As a result, energy efficiency increases, start-up processes are smoothed, and the functional capabilities of electromechanical systems are significantly expanded [3,4,5].

The theoretical basis of state observers is explained by their basis in a mathematical model, the stability and flexibility of the dynamics of the observation error. The observer equations contain special adjustment coefficients, the so-called L-matrix, which determine the speed of the observer dynamics and its ability to adapt to the system. A correctly selected L-matrix ensures a rapid decay of the observer error and accelerates the adaptation of the model to a real object. In this respect, observer synthesis is similar to regulator synthesis, and the principle of duality between control and observation processes is of important methodological importance. According to this principle, the mathematical approaches used in the design of the regulator can also be used in the synthesis of the observer. This theoretical unity creates great convenience in scientific research and practical design processes. The practical importance of observer synthesis is even more evident in the example of electric drives. In conditions where the load torque, internal magnetic changes or mechanical resistances cannot be continuously measured, the observer identifies the corresponding signal and ensures the appropriate compensation of the system. This feature increases the system's resistance to external noise, load jumps, and mechanical changes. [6,7,8] Due to the use of an astatic observer in high-precision electric drives, it is possible to take into account zero-frequency effects. Discrete analogs of observers are widely used in microcontrollers, digital control systems, and real-time industrial devices. The advantage of a discrete observer is that the algorithms run directly on the device in the form of code, which results in increased sensitivity and speed of the system. The structure of the digital observer equations includes the processes of prior estimation, error calculation, and final state update. The sequence of these processes corresponds to the operating cycle of the microcontroller and ensures continuous updating of the control signals. As

a result of the joint operation of the observer and the regulator, the control system can filter complex external influences, the stability of the system increases, energy losses are reduced, and the overall efficiency of the process increases. Thus, the synthesis of state observers has not only theoretical significance, but also significant scientific and practical value as an effective approach widely used in the optimization of real industrial processes.

Research Methods and the Received Results

A state observer of a controlled object is essentially a configurable model of that object. This model can be formulated in coordinates that are convenient for synthesizing the state controller. Technically, a state observer (SO) is usually implemented as a subroutine of a control algorithm, i.e. its use does not add any technical complexity to the control system [9].

Thus, the observer consists of a model of the controlled object.

$$\dot{x} = Ax + bU, (1)$$

where x – the vector of observed (calculated) object coordinates;

A, b – the coefficient matrices taken from the description of the object's dynamics;

U – the control action, which is applied to the object and simultaneously through the ADC converter to its model (observer).

This model is adjusted as a function of the observation error, which is defined as the difference between the measurable output signal of the controlled object and the output signal from the model:

$$\varepsilon_H = Y - C\dot{x} = C(x - \dot{x}), (2)$$

By combining these expressions into one closed system through the matrix of setting coefficients L, we obtain the equation of a complete state observer [10]:

$$\dot{x} = Ax + bU + L(Y - Cx). (3)$$

After presenting such terms, we obtain the observer's description of the object's condition in the following form:

$$\dot{x} = (A - LC)x + LY + bU, (4)$$

where - object state estimation vector; - matrix of estimation vector subconstruction coefficients.

As can be seen from (3), if the initial state of the observer and the state of the object differ, then under the influence of negative feedback, the observation error tends to zero. In this way, the construction of the object model (1) will be carried out, and the values of its internal coordinates after the completion of the transition construction process will coincide with the values of the corresponding internal coordinates of the object. Strictly speaking, the observer (3) is the observer of the initial conditions [11].

From (4) it follows that the self-movement of the observer's adjustment process is determined by the expression.

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$$\dot{x} = e^{(A-LC)t} x. \quad (5)$$

From (5), it follows that by selecting the coefficients of the L matrix, it is possible to ensure the required type of transient processes of the observer's adjustment.

The use of an observer, as already noted, allows you to abandon the sensors of internal coordinates of the object when it is impossible or impractical to install these sensors. For example, all coordinates of the state of an electric drive (current, speed, angle) can be changed in principle. However, with microprocessor control, the number of sensors needs to be minimized. In addition, to improve the quality of regulation, it is often necessary to determine the dynamic and static components of the current. Therefore, in this case, it is advisable to use an observer [12].

The developed structural diagram of the closed system "control object + state observer + state regulator" (CO+SN+SR), corresponding to the diagram in Fig. 4.1, c, is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Control system with observer and state regulator (with dynamic RS)

A state regulator with an observer is also called a dynamic observer. Obviously, the additional inclusion of an observer will affect the overall dynamics of the system, increasing the duration of transient processes compared to the duration of these processes in the system with a state regulator without an observer. Therefore, when calculating the CO+SR+SN system, it is necessary to simultaneously calculate the matrix coefficients K and L.

The calculation task is simplified due to the property of separation of management and observation processes. This can be proven in the following way. Vector of deviations of the observer's position coordinates from the object's position coordinates [13]

$\Delta x = x - \hat{x}$, in accordance with the structural diagram in Fig. 1, is defined by the following system of differential equations, represented in matrix form, $\Delta \dot{x} = \dot{x} - \dot{\hat{x}} = Ax - bKx + bU - A\hat{x} + bK\hat{x} - bU - LC(x - \hat{x})$

Or after introducing such members, we will get $\Delta \dot{x} = (A - LC)\Delta x$ (6)

Considering $\dot{x} = x - \Delta x$, free movement will be described by the following equation

$$\dot{x} = Ax - bK(x - \Delta x) = (A - bK)x + bK\Delta x \quad (7)$$

Equations (4) and (5) are represented in a single matrix form, which will describe the free motion of the system CO+SN+SR:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \Delta \dot{x} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A - bK & bK \\ 0 & A - LC \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ \Delta x \end{bmatrix}$$

Consequently, the characteristic equation of a closed system will have the form

$$\det \begin{bmatrix} PI(A - bK) & -bK \\ 0 & PI - (A - LC) \end{bmatrix} = 0$$

From where do we get that the characteristic equation will be equal to the product of the characteristic equation of the system CO+SR and the characteristic equation SN

$$D_c(p) = \det[PI - (A - bK)] \det[PI - (A - LC)] = 0$$

From this it follows that this equation can be represented as two independent characteristic equations:

$$\det[PI - (A - bK)] = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\det[PI - (A - LC)] = 0. \quad (5)$$

This makes it possible to independently synthesize the state regulator without taking into account the presence of a state observer and to synthesize a separate state observer. But the total time of transient processes in the CO+NS+RS system will be determined by the sum of the roots of both equations (4) and (5). Therefore, the coefficients of the matrix L must be chosen from the condition that the free movement of the observer is 3-5 times faster than in the CO+RS system. In this case, the presence of an observer increases the total duration of transient processes by 20% [14].

Another remarkable property used in the synthesis of the observer is called the duality of the control and observation processes.

In equation (3), unlike the equation of a system with a state regulator (1), the known matrix C is a row matrix, and the search matrix L is a column matrix (in (2), the search matrix K is a row matrix). To apply the methodology for determining the state regulator coefficients matrix K to determine the state observer's L-matrix settings, we use the property that the transposable matrix has the same characteristic equation as the initial matrix. Thanks to this property

$$\det[A^T - L^T C^T] = \det[PI - (A - LC)] = 0,$$

where T – transposition sign;

C^T – column-matrix;

L^T – stroke matrix.

From this it follows that if the control object $\xi = A^T \xi + C^T v$ and the state regulator $v = -L^T \xi$ are taken, then the determination of the adjustment matrix coefficients of the L observer leads to the task of determining the elements of the L^T matrix as coefficients of the state regulator for the $\xi = (A^T - C^T L^T) \xi$ system.

Let's consider the synthesis of SN according to this methodology for an electric drive control system. The observer will have a second order, since the output measured coordinate is the velocity x_2 , and the coordinate x_1 can be excluded from the object description. On the other hand, to identify the stimulating effect (moment of load on the electric motor), we will expand this model by connecting an additional integrating link to the point where this effect should be applied. Such an observer is called astatic due to the presence of an integrator in the circuit of the substructure [15].

At the output of the additional integrator, after the adjustment process, a signal equal to the magnitude of the disturbing effect appears.

By entering the notation $i_H = x_4$, according to the following description of the object is obtained:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_2 \\ \dot{x}_3 \\ \dot{x}_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & a_{23} & a_{24} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} b \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} u, \quad (13)$$

$$Y = [1 \ 0 \ 0] \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}^T,$$

where $a_{24} = h_2$.

The coefficient matrices of the conjugate system will be as follows:

$$A^T = \bar{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & a_{23} & a_{24} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \quad C^T = \bar{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

We are given the reference matrix A_E of the form (12) with the binomial form of the coefficients of the characteristic equation.

By substituting (14) into (6), the direct and inverse transforming matrices are determined.

$$\bar{P} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -a_{33} & 1 \\ 0 & a_{23} & 0 \\ -a_{24}a_{33} & a_{24} & 0 \end{bmatrix};$$

$$\bar{P}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & a_{23}^{-1}a_{33}^{-1} & -a_{23}^{-1}a_{33}^{-1} \\ 0 & a_{23}^{-1} & 0 \\ 1 & a_{33}a_{23}^{-1} & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \quad (15)$$

A regulator that provides the $A-C^T L^T$ matrix with the same eigenvalues as the reference matrix can be determined from an equation analogous to (5)

$$C^T L^T = A - P A_E P^{-1} \quad (17)$$

Substituting (5), (16), and (17) into equation (16), we obtain

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} l_{11} & l_{12} & l_{13} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & a_{32} & 0 \\ a_{23} & a_{33} & 0 \\ a_{24} & a_{34} & 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -a_{32} & 1 \\ 0 & a_{23} & 0 \\ -a_{24}a_{32} & a_{24} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -a_{E0} & -a_{E1} & -a_{E2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & a_{23}^{-1}a_{33}^{-1} & -a_{23}^{-1}a_{33}^{-1} \\ 0 & a_{23}^{-1} & 0 \\ 1 & a_{33}a_{23}^{-1} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

By solving this matrix equation, the elements of the matrix L are determined. L

$$l_{11} = \ddot{a}_{E2} + a_{33}; \quad l_{13} = \frac{-\ddot{a}_{E0}}{a_{24}a_{33}};$$

$$l_{12} = \frac{-\ddot{a}_{E0} + \ddot{a}_{E1}a_{33} + a_{23}a_{32}a_{33} + \ddot{a}_{E2}a_{33}^2 + a_{33}^2}{a_{24}a_{33}};$$

(18)

The observer has insignificant influence on the time of transient processes if the eigenvalues of the matrices $(A-BK)$ and $(A-LC)$ do not intersect. Consequently, in the binomial form of the coefficients of the characteristic equation A_E , this requirement reduces to inequality [16,17].

$$|\ddot{q}| > q_1,$$

where \ddot{q} – the eigenvalue of matrix \ddot{A}_E , multiple of trem.

This condition is a limitation of $|\ddot{q}|$ from below. The limitation above is determined from the condition of noise filtration efficiency. Based on these

premises, the value is usually taken 3 ÷ 5 times greater than $|\ddot{q}|$.

Substituting into (1) from (2) and (3) the values of the coefficients expressed through and the engine parameters gives the following expressions for the elements of the L matrix

$$l_{11} = \frac{1}{T_y} (3qT_y - 1); \quad l_{13} = \frac{\mathfrak{I}}{C_y} \ddot{q}T_y;$$

$$l_{12} = \frac{\mathfrak{I}}{C_y} \left(-\ddot{q}^3 T_y + 3\ddot{q}^2 - 3\frac{q}{T_y} + \frac{1}{T_y^2} - \frac{1}{T_y T_M} \right) + \ddot{q}T_y$$

The resulting system structure with a state controller and an observer is shown in Figure 2. Unlike the structure in Figure 1, the object includes a power converter with a gain of KP and a speed sensor with a gain of KD. Accordingly, the feedback and correction coefficients of the observer change their values:

$$K_\alpha \frac{K_1}{K_P K_D}; \quad K_\Omega \frac{K_2}{K_P K_D}; \quad K_i \frac{K_1}{K_P}; \quad l_{li} \frac{l_{li}}{K_D}$$

The synthesized observer further improves the control system's dynamics in response to external disturbances, as this disturbance is identified. In Figure 1, the dashed line shows the compensating relationship for the load current i_H .

Fig. 2. Structural diagram of an astatic engine speed control system with a state regulator and an observer

When describing an object discretely, the equation of a discrete observer by analogy with the

equation of a continuous observer (20) will have the following form.

$$\ddot{x}[k+1] = (A^* - CL)x[k] + b^*U[k]. \quad (21)$$

The equation of the conjugate system, by means of which the matrix of the subset \mathbf{L} is determined, as for the continuous model, will have the form

$$\begin{aligned} \xi[k+1] &= A^T \xi[k] + C^T v[k]; \\ v[k] &= L^T \xi[k] \quad (22); \end{aligned}$$

Considering that

$$A^{*T} = [e^{AT}] = e^{A^T T} = e^{\ddot{A}T},$$

the free motion of a conjugate system is determined by the equation.

$$\xi[k+1] = (e^{AT} - C^T L^T) \xi[k]. \quad (23)$$

The reference discrete model of free motion is determined by the following dependence

$$\xi[k+1] = (e^{A_E T} \eta[k]). \quad (24)$$

If the coordinate bases of models (22) and (24) coincide, then the observer's matrix is determined from the equality of the models' dynamic matrices

$$e^{AT} - C^T L^{*T} = e^{A_E T} \quad \text{or} \quad C^T L^{*T} = e^{AT} - e^{A_E T}.$$

If the bases do not coincide, they should be determined by linear transformation. $\xi = P\eta$,

Then $A_E^{*T} = e^{PA_E P^{-1}T}$, and the observer's construction matrix will be determined from the equation

$$C^T L^{*T} = e^{AT} - e^{PA_E P^{-1}T}. \quad (25)$$

Let us consider the definition of the matrix \mathbf{L} when approximating discrete models according to Euler. The transition matrix of the system (21), approximated by Euler, as well as in the case of state regulator synthesis, will be determined by the following expression:

$$\tilde{A}_3^* = I + PAP^{-1}T.$$

For the transition reference matrix

$$\tilde{A}^* = I + PA_E P^{-1}T.$$

From the equality of these matrices, it follows that

$$C^T \tilde{L}^T = (A - PAP^{-1})T. \quad (26)$$

Expression (26) differs from expression (19) only in that its right side is multiplied by the scalar quantity T . Consequently, when using a discrete model approximated by Euler's method, the elements of the observer's adjustment matrix can be determined using a continuous model, followed by multiplying each element by the sampling period.

The combination of discrete controller and discrete observer equations provides algorithms for direct microprocessor control of the object (particularly an electric motor) in the range of small deviations. To obtain a recursive algorithm, we divide the observer equation (21) into two components: the equation for obtaining an a priori estimate of the state vector, denoted as \mathbf{X}^0 ,

$$x_\alpha[k+1] = A^* x[k] + b^* U[k], \quad (27)$$

and the direct observer equation (or estimate adjustment equation)

$$x[k] = x_\alpha[k] + L^*(Y[k] - Cx_\alpha[k]). \quad (28)$$

Let's write down the equation for determining the regulation error

$$\varepsilon[k] = V[k] - Y[k] \quad (29)$$

and equation of the regulator

$$U[k] = K_\alpha \left(\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \varepsilon[i] + \varepsilon[k] \right) + K_\Omega \varepsilon[k] - K_r x_3[k] + K_f x_4[k]. \quad (30)$$

Figure 3. State controller and observer algorithm flowchart

Figure 3 shows the flowchart of the algorithm combining the state controller and observer equations.

The algorithm operates as follows. First, the measuring (block 2) and control (block 1) devices are polled. In the first step, initial conditions are assigned to the state estimate vector (blocks 3 and 4). In the following steps, the observed coordinates (block 5) are determined using equation (28) based on the a priori estimate obtained in the previous step (block 9, equation (27)) and the output coordinate measured in the current step (block 2). Next, the control error (block 6, equation (29)) and the control action (block 7, equation (30)) are determined, which is sent to the actuator (block 8). This algorithm meets the requirements for direct microprocessor control algorithms:

1. The parameters of the object model are directly related to the easily measurable and calculable coordinates of the object.

2. The controller parameters are calculated based on the process model parameters without repetition and using the simplest method.

3. Calculations related to management are carried out in accordance with the speed of data receipt.

CONCLUSION

This article presents a scientifically substantiated theoretical foundation for synthesizing state observers and the potential for their application in modern control systems. The results of the study demonstrate that a state observer is an important tool for effectively organizing the control process under conditions of limited direct measurement of internal states. The correct selection of the L-matrix defining the observer's dynamics is crucial for ensuring stability, performance, and accuracy of system state assessment. The principle of separability of control and observation processes and the duality between them strengthen the methodological basis for synthesizing observers and simplify the design process. The practical effectiveness of observers in detecting and compensating for external influences is confirmed using an electric motor as an example, demonstrating the high relevance of their use in

industrial control systems. Furthermore, the operation of discrete observers based on a microcontroller ensures high accuracy and reliability in real time in digital control systems.

Based on the above, the following recommendations can be made: When designing control systems, the L-matrix parameters for the observer should be selected in accordance with stability and performance requirements. In electromechanical systems, especially under variable load conditions, the use of astatic observers allows for the effective identification of external disturbances. When working with digital controls, discrete observer models must be adapted to the microcontroller's sampling period. During the design process, it is advisable to pre-simulate the interaction between the observer and the controller and minimize their impact on the system's dynamics. To reduce the impact of noise and improve estimation accuracy, it is recommended to use filtering and adaptive tuning mechanisms in the observer's internal algorithms.

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